

The Assessment of Level IV Training Impact on Commercial Bank of Ethiopia's the Central Addis Ababa Region Financial and Non-Financial Performances during the 2022/23 Fiscal Year

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Abstract

This study assesses the impact of training programs on both the financial and non-financial performance of the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia (CBE) during the 2022/23 fiscal year, using the Phillips Five-Level Training Evaluation Model as its analytical framework. The evaluation focuses on technical, developmental, and ethical training programs, examining outcomes across four levels: reaction, learning, behaviour, and business results. Due to data limitations, the Return on Investment (ROI) level was excluded from the analysis. A mixed-methods approach was employed, incorporating quantitative and qualitative data collected through surveys, interviews, focus group discussions (FGDs), and secondary data sources, including bank performance records. A multi-stage sampling strategy ensured representation across regions, organizational levels, and customer segments. The findings show that training programs contributed significantly to key financial indicators such as deposit mobilization, liquidity, and operational efficiency. Paired sample t-tests revealed statistically significant improvements in post-training test scores, particularly in technical and developmental training. Regression analysis indicated a positive and sustained impact of training on employee performance as measured by appraisal scores. However, the alignment between training content and business goals was found to be inconsistent, limiting the effectiveness in some areas—especially customer acquisition and satisfaction. On the non-financial side, training supported enhancements in public image, employee discipline, and technology leadership. Nonetheless, its influence on service quality, job satisfaction, and corporate client relations was less impactful, hindered by external factors like resource limitations and workplace environment. The study concludes that while training has a clear value, its full potential can only be realized through better alignment with strategic objectives, improved follow-up systems, and integrated performance management frameworks

Keywords: Commercial Bank of Ethiopia (CBE), training evaluation, Phillips model, financial performance, non-financial impact, human resource development, learning transfer, employee performance, organizational effectiveness, training ROI.

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Context of the Study

This study aims to evaluate the impact of training programs on both the financial and non-financial performance of the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia (CBE), using the Phillips Model as the foundational assessment framework. The Phillips Model assesses training effectiveness across five levels: reaction, learning, behavior change, results (learning impact), and return on investment (ROI). The study focuses on analyzing the financial effects of CBE's training programs such as improvements in deposit mobilization, liquidity, and customer acquisition as well as non-financial (intangible) benefits, including enhanced public image, increased

employee satisfaction, improved service quality, and strengthened organizational commitment. While the model includes ROI as a critical component, this study delimits its scope by excluding the ROI level due to data limitations and the complexity of quantifying exact monetary returns on training investments. Instead, it places greater emphasis on assessing measurable outcomes at the individual and organizational levels, providing insights to inform future training strategies and policy decisions within the bank.

1.2. Rationale & need for the study

CBE has heavily invested in human capital development through training programs across technical, developmental, and ethical categories. A total of 79,533 trainees were enrolled during 2022.23 FY with an investment of more than 7.1 million USD.

However, there has been less practice in evaluating the effectiveness or impact of these programs on financial and non-financial returns. Thus, to ensure human capital development investments lead to tangible improvements in business performance and employee productivity this study were conducted.

1.3. Objectives of the Study

This study was conducted to assess the impact of the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia's (CBE) training programs on both the financial and non-financial performance of the bank during the 2022/23 fiscal year. The general objective was to evaluate how these training initiatives influenced the bank's overall outcomes. Specifically, the study aimed to critically examine the effectiveness of CBE's technical, developmental, and ethical training programs implemented during the fiscal year, using Phillips' model of training evaluation. Additionally, it sought to measure the financial and non-financial benefits derived from these training interventions, with particular emphasis on their impact on employee performance and broader business outcomes.

II. LITRATURE REVIEW

2.1. Overview of Human Resource Development

For an organization operating in a highly dynamic environment, employees' education, training, and development should be part of its organizational strategy. This is related with the idea that "human beings purposefully developing themselves to improve the conditions in which they are in" (Saks & Haccoun, 2019).

Human Resource Development (HRD) is a set of systematic and planned activities designed by an organization to provide its members with the opportunities to learn necessary skills to meet current and future job demands (Swanson, 2022). It is also defined as a process of developing and unleashing expertise to improve individual, team, work process, and organizational system performance. Developing knowledge, expertise, productivity, and satisfaction can benefit people at individual, group, organizational, community, or ultimately at humanity levels (Werner and DeSimone, 2012).

As part of the HRD program of a company, training works on changing or improving the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of individuals; and development has a long -term focus on preparing for future work responsibilities while also increasing the capacities of employees to perform their current jobs. Besides, HRD is a conscious practice where organizations assess human potentials, selectively upgrade, and appropriately deploy for achievement of envisioned goals (Mankin, 2001). Hence, HRD involves consideration of many factors and authorities in the interrelationship and interdependence among these factors in the form of HRD Models.

The effectiveness of HRD program in general and T&D program in particular is the result of the interplay of many factors. Most studies assess the effectiveness of training programs within a broader context through rigorous evaluation of internal and external influencers (Hendry & Pettigrew, 1990). Accordingly, authorities propose different evaluation models, which are different in terms of level of emphasis, number of variables, considered, and the level of

analysis. The following paragraphs briefly discuss the most popular and frequently used HRD model called Phillips and Holton training evaluation model.

2.2. Phillips and Holton Five-level Training Evaluation Model (1995).

Phillips is known in the evaluation field for his focus on Return on Investment (ROI). His evaluation model is largely comparable to Kirkpatrick, but adds a fifth level to separate out the assessment of the monetary benefits of the training compared to its costs. The levels are:

Level 1: Reaction and planned action — which also includes a plan of what participants intend to apply from the program

Level 2: Learning

Level 3: Job application

Level 4: Business results

Level 5: Return on Investment

Unlike Kirkpatrick model, Phillips model emphasizes both ROI and intangible benefits or business results. Business results are assessed using measures such as quality, cost, time, and customer satisfaction ratings. The fifth layer of the model gives particular attention to ROI. Each phase of the training evaluation model is discussed as follows:

Level 1: Reaction Phase of Training Evaluation

The purpose of evaluating at the reaction level is primarily to assess what the participants initially thought and felt about the training and development program. End of course reaction questionnaire is usually used to collect data about trainees. This training evaluation phase is important because unhappy participants will probably not learn very much. Examining trainees' reactions to the training helps in improving the planning and designing of the training as well as understanding of the eventual success or otherwise of the training. Tannenbaum et al. (1991) also found out that the extent to which training meets or fulfills a trainee's expectations and desires (i.e., training fulfillment), trainees' reaction, and training performance have significant effect on post-training attitudes of trainees.

Level 2: The Learning Phase of Training Evaluation

Evaluation at a learning level provides data on the degree of change to knowledge, skills or attitude stemming from the program, and is normally assessed using some type of performance tests, or by participant and line manager feedback on the extent of learning that has taken place. There is a high level of agreement in the literature that, ideally, measures of performance need to be taken both before and after the training event, to be able to assess gains in learning. Methods for testing learning have become quite sophisticated, with techniques such as criterion-referenced testing (Shrock and Coscarelli, 1989).

Erikson (1990) distinguishes between operational knowledge and theoretical knowledge. He argues that a trainee can repeat theories, giving the appearance of learning, but may be unable to apply it. Consequently, testing learning without putting it in context will not show the value.

Level 3: Behavior and the Transfer of Learning

There is no one clear conceptualization of training transfer; and such variations in definition influence the way they are studied (Schoeb et al., 2021). Some of the conceptualizations include: first, training transfer refers to how often new learning or behavior is applied in the workplace; second, it is defined as the quality or effectiveness of the application of new learning; and third, it is defined as an improvement in workplace performance once the new learning has been applied (Schoeb et al., 2021). 'Transfer of training is the application of the knowledge and skills acquired in a training program on the job and the maintenance of acquired knowledge and skills overtime. The use or application of learned materials to the job is known as generalization; and the use or application of learned material on the job over a period of time is known as maintenance (Saks & Haccoun, 2019).

Level 4: Effect of Training on Business Results

It is universally agreed that evaluation at the behavioral and results levels are made more difficult due to the fact that training is not the only relevant causal factor. The further one attempts to measure the impact from the training event itself, the greater the difficulty in attributing cause and effect (Tamkin et al., 2002). Despite this, the literature suggests that there is an increasing concern in organizations to justify the investment in training in terms of improved organizational performance, such as increased productivity, profit or safety, reduced error and enhanced market share.

The process of linking training to business results is highly interpretative, especially in complex business environments. Pulley (1994) argues that what is needed is 'responsive evaluation' which pays attention to both hard and soft issues and provides both quantitative and qualitative measures.

Beyond its ultimate effect on financial return, training has such contributions as enhancing employees' performance, boosting employees' productivity, reducing employees' turnover, and improving company's culture; it also increases job satisfaction, organizational commitment, improved teamwork, improved customer service, reduced complaints, and reduced conflicts.

2.3. Analytical Framework

According to Phillips (2002), when evaluating the ultimate results of training (determining return on investment), it is important to validate the preceding phases such as assessing trainees' satisfaction, the knowledge acquired by trainees, the application of knowledge acquired in the workplace, and the business results of the training. Figure 6 displays the training evaluation model proposed by Phillips. Our study predicts that training can yield significant benefits that can be revealed in the key performance indicators such as increased revenue, reduced costs, and enhanced profitability. Furthermore, we believe that training has the potential to increase customer satisfaction, improve service quality, boost employees' morale, and foster the bank's image. While the payoffs are assumed to exist and training appears to be needed, more evidence is required, or training funds may not be allocated in the future. The ROI methodology is the most promising approach to demonstrate accountability in a logical and sensible manner.

In summary, the study will carry out the following phases:

- **Phase I:** Validate the trainees' reaction and satisfaction with the training delivered through reviewing of reports, evaluation of training processes, and primary data.
- **Phase II:** Validating whether training held has improved the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of participants.
- **Phase III:** Validating whether the participants' knowledge, skills, and attitudes are transferred to the jobs they assigned.
- **Phase IV:** Analyze whether the application of knowledge, skills, and changes in attitude acquired during the training program have enhanced both tangible and intangible aspects of the business.
- **Phase V:** Calculate the return on investment (ROI) of the training program by applying different methods.

Figure 1: Training Evaluation Model

III. METEHOLOGY

3.1. Summary of Research Methodology

A combination qualitative and quantitative research design was used. Primary data were gathered through surveys, Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), and Key Informant Interviews (KIIs), while secondary data included bank records and reports.

1.3.1. Data Sources

Primary data were collected via surveys, KIIs, and FGDs, targeting employees, corporate clients, middle-level managers, and senior and executive managers. Specific information was gathered from district directors, HR managers, and employees who participated in training during the year 2022.23 FY. In addition, secondary were sourced from training databases, performance management systems, HR records, financial reports, and relevant organizational documents.

1.3.2. Quantitative Data Sampling

A multi-stage sampling method was used and the details of quantitative and qualitative sampling techniques used. The study covered various categories using tailored sampling methods to ensure comprehensive and representative data collection. Out of 10 districts, 6 were selected using random sampling to ensure geographical diversity. From the 312 branches across these districts, 132 branches were chosen 22 per district again using random sampling to maintain both branch diversity and geographical coverage. At the branch level, each branch had 2 supervisors, totaling 309 supervisors; this included a fixed selection of 264 branch supervisors and a random sample of 45 from the Head Office, to gather insights from key branch management.

For employees, 487 were randomly selected 3 per branch to capture diverse perspectives at the operational level. Among the 22 Vice Presidents (Executives), 5 were randomly sampled to reflect leadership viewpoints. All 6 District Directors from the selected districts were included through a complete enumeration (census) to ensure representation from senior district-level

management. At the Head Office, 36 out of 105 directors were randomly selected to represent senior management perspectives. Finally, 344 corporate customers were included based on availability sampling, capturing input from those willing to participate.

1.3.3. Qualitative Data Sampling

The data collection for the study involved a combination of Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) at both district and head office levels, using a mix of sampling methods tailored to each group. At the district level, 18 key informants participated in KIIs, selected through a mixed sampling method comprising the District Director, the HR Business Partner, and one manager randomly selected from each of the six districts.

Additionally, six FGDs were conducted at the district level, each comprising 10 randomly selected managers from their respective districts, totaling 60 participants. At the head office, 12 key informants were selected for KIIs using stratified sampling, with 3 individuals chosen from each category: professional employees, managers, directors, and vice presidents, to ensure representation across different organizational levels. Furthermore, two FGDs were conducted at the head office, involving a total of 24 participants 12 managers and 12 professionals randomly selected to provide a balanced view from both management and professional staff.

3.2. Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and Phillips' ROI model were applied to assess the impact of training on business results. Data were processed using SPSS or STATA software. Moreover, transcribed interviews and FGDs were analyzed for emerging themes and triangulated with quantitative findings for deeper insights. Furthermore, the study follows the Phillips model, which assesses training across five levels: reaction, learning, behavior change, learning impact.

IV. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Reaction level Analysis Result 1st Level

Trainees were asked to rate the content, methods, trainer, and facilities of training sessions they attended out of 5 marks and results were converted to 100 for the simplicity of analysis. Overall, trainees rated training sessions as highly satisfactory in the developmental (Mean=0.91), ethical (Mean=0.91) and technical (Mean=0.87) training categories.

4.2. Paired Sample T-Test (Pre and Post training Test Results) 2d Level

In the technical training category, pre-training and post-training tests are moderately correlated ($r = 0.570$; $p < 0.001$); the mean difference between pre-training and post-training tests was significant ($t = 45.90$; $p < 0.001$); and on average, post-test scores were 13.10 points higher than pre-test scores.

In the ethical training category, pre-training and post-training tests had very weak correlation ($r = 0.081$; $p < 0.001$); the mean difference between pre-training and post-training tests was significant ($t = 4.31$; $p < 0.001$); and on average, post-test scores were 1.780 points higher than pre-test scores.

4.3. Assessing Transfer of Training to the Workplace (3rd Level)

Taking performance data from the bank's performance management system (PMS) for each employee, we regressed it against lags of one period training and evaluated the impacts based on the following regression model.

$$(\text{Appraisal})_{(i,t)} = \alpha_{(i,t-1)} (\text{Appraisal})_{(i,t)} + \beta_1 (\text{Training})_{(i,t-1)} + \beta_2 (\text{Training})_{(i,t-2)} + \beta_4 (\text{Education})_i + \beta_5 (\text{Experience})_i + \beta_6 (\text{Age})_i + \beta_7 (\text{Gender})_i + e_{it}$$

The results we documented show that the training program has statistically significant positive relationship with the appraisal score. Employees who took more training have obtained higher appraisal score. The effect has been intensified for the second lag (one year's lags)

4.4. Impact of Training on Business Results: Secondary Data Analysis (4th level)

Trainings had a positive and significant fixed effect on change in interest income ($\beta=.265$, $p<.01$), and net interest margin ($\beta=22.515$, $P<.01$) at one year time lag.

4.5. Impact of Training on Financial Performance (Over all respondents Score)

The survey revealed that, overall, training has contributions to financial performance improvement (Mean = 3.66). Particularly, respondents agreed that trainings had greater contributions to the improvement of deposit mobilization (Mean = 4.02) and operating efficiency (Mean= 4.02) improvements. The survey results also indicate that training has significant roles in reducing operating expense (Mean= 3.64), improving liquidity (Mean= 3.68), improving non-performing loan (Mean= 3.59) and increasing foreign currency exchanges (Mean= 3.53). Similarly, findings obtained from interview, FGD, secondary data sources supported the result. The findings are also consistent with panel data regression analysis result

4.6. Contributions of Training to Intangible Benefits

CBE's training has significant contributions to improve the public image of the bank (Mean = 3.99), improve organizational commitment of employees (Mean = 3.73), and facilitate technology leadership strategy (Mean = 3.89). On the other hand, the contributions of training to improve customer service quality (Mean = 3.62) and enhance employees job satisfaction (Mean = 3.72) were rated as moderate. The training sessions at CBE have an impact on building a positive culture in terms of cultivating teamwork, appreciating diversity, and promoting positive behavior. However, its role in promoting equity, fairness, and a sense of belongingness was not at the expected level. Similarly, findings obtained from interview, FGD, secondary data sources supported the result. The findings are also consistent with panel data regression analysis result.

In the developmental training category, pre-training and post-training tests had weak correlation ($r =0.336$; $p<0.001$); the mean difference between pre-training and post-training tests was significant ($t=54.44$; $p<0.001$); and on average, post-test scores were 19.88 points higher than pre-test scores. Overall, pre-training and post-training tests had weak correlation ($r =0.386$; $p<0.001$); the mean difference between pre-training and post-training tests was significant ($t=67.41$; $p<0.001$); and on average, post-test scores were 13.01 points higher than pre-test scores.

The results imply weak correlation between training and learning. In relative terms, the effect of training on employees learning was better for technical trainings, had average some effect on developmental training

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the analysis of primary and secondary data, we draw the following conclusions and recommendations:

- Training significantly contributed to enhancing employees' ability to mobilize deposits, improve liquidity, and boost operational efficiency. However, its impact was uneven across performance indicators. This may be due to a weak alignment between training design—such as objectives, content, methods, and delivery—and the bank's business goals, as well as inconsistencies in the structure and sequencing of competency-building programs related to key performance indicators (KPIs).
- The effect of training to improve the bank's customer base via recruiting new customers was not at the expected level. This might happen because of factors other than the performance

capacity of employees. Such factors include competition, socio-economic, and political situations. As mentioned in the previous sections, external factors have also influenced the effectiveness of CBE's training program.

- CBE's training programs offer positive intangible benefits, like enhancing public image and supporting technology leadership. However, their impact on job satisfaction, employee engagement, service quality, and customer satisfaction especially among corporate clients remains below expectations. This is partly due to external factors such as unsupportive work environments, limited resources, and inadequate supervision. Thus, training alone is insufficient; strategic leadership and integrated systems thinking are essential to link training efforts with overall organizational performance.
- The training sessions of CBE have impact in building positive culture in terms of cultivating team work, appreciating diversity, and promoting positive behaviour.
- The effect of CBE's training in building ethical behaviour related to appearance, discipline, confidentiality, and respect is high; and its effect in promoting fairness, professional competency, and punctuality was moderate. This might imply that beyond the need to implement strong follow-up and control activities, successful implementation of ethical behaviours needs training that assist employees to practice such behaviours. This was consistent with finding that ethical trainings have low impact than technical trainings of CBE.
- Implementing performance management systems like KPIs helps set clear goals, monitor progress, and improve service quality by aligning employee efforts with organizational objectives. Focusing on employee performance and satisfaction boosts customer experience and business growth. Additionally, training programs should account for external socio-economic and political factors through continuous environmental analysis to stay relevant and effective.

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